

What opinions do LLMs/chatbots have about OpenStreetMap?

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Large Language Models (LLMs) are pretrained on vast amounts of human data and it is reasonable to assume that LLMs can reflect the AOVs (Attitudes, Opinions and Values) embedded in the data [1]. LLMs are increasingly being used in open-ended contexts, where the opinions they reflect in response to subjective queries can have a profound impact on shaping the views of society at large [2]. LLMs/chatbots can be prompted to generate opinion-like text. For example, in Malleson et. al [3] LLMs are used to give opinions on neighbourhood change. The huge popularity of these chatbots means that opinionated text produced by LLMs/chatbots can have the potential to be very influential on the user [4,5]. When LLMs are integrated into search engines, social platforms, and other interactive systems, their outputs when the user is seeking opinions or viewpoints can become a user's first—or only—exposure to a topic [5]. We have concerns around how LLMs can shape how OpenStreetMap (OSM) is used in the future and therefore our work aims to understand potential biases or negative opinions produced by LLMs/chatbots when learning about OSM. We investigate the opinions or views expressed by some of the major current LLMs when prompted or questioned about their opinions on specific aspects of OSM. We make the assumption that LLMs will have been trained on data and information related to OSM and in particular legacy topics such as: data quality, comparison with official or authoritative sources, accuracy, bias in crowdsourced data, and so on. Our research question asks: can we quantitatively and qualitatively understand the AOVs of LLMs around topics related to OSM? To the best of our knowledge, there is no research currently reported about this topic. The majority of work published about LLMs and OSM revolves around using the LLMs as mapping assistants [6,7] or using LLMs to enrich existing data or allow more accessible approaches to mapping [8]. Other works have considered the ability of chatbots such as ChatGPT to take a GIS exam [9], exploit the deep contextual understandings in LLMs for building function classification in OSM [10], or enhance accessibility to GIS using AI (as in [9]). Our work steps back from this by investigating how LLMs/chatbots can be influential in informing opinions about crowdsourced geospatial data and its usage within GIS applications and research. We do this by instructing LLMs to perform two tasks related to the following topics: geospatial data quality, temporal currency of OSM data and overall sentiment towards OSM.

Each topic of inquiry consisted of a qualitative and a quantitative task. Prompts were designed to elicit structured outputs in JSON format which ensures consistency across

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responses. Models were queried through the University of Florida NaviGator Chat interface [11], which is a customized version of the open-source Open WebUI [12] enabling calls to multiple chatbots hosted on different backends. We tested different variants of commonly used LLMs/chatbots, including Gemini (Google), GPT (OpenAI), Mistral (Mistral AI), Llama (Meta), Claude (Anthropic) and Nova (Amazon). UF NaviGator Chat allowed uniform control of generation parameters (*random seed=123, temperature=0, top_p=0.00000001*) that ultimately ensured that responses were as deterministic as possible, unaffected by different configurations of commercial chat interfaces. Additionally, the same system prompt was used for each task to establish a consistent framing, and a new session was started for each task. An additional prominent chatbot, Grok-4 (xAI) was also included, but queried separately through its web interface due to platform constraints. Responses were collected as JSON documents and subsequently parsed into spreadsheets. For the qualitative tasks, themes were manually identified from chatbot explanations and reasons, and synthesized into summary categories. For quantitative tasks, numerical outputs were aggregated. All chatbot versions, prompts, system settings and raw responses are available as Supplementary Material for transparency and reproducibility. Given the volume of results generated, for brevity, we focus on the following aspects of the tasks: the quality of OSM, the temporal currency of OSM, and the overall sentiment towards OSM shown by the LLMs/chatbots.

The quality of OSM: 12 out of 15 chatbots responded “Yes” to the question whether OSM is a high quality source of geospatial data, which suggests that generally LLMs/chatbots recognize the value of OSM. The main reason supporting high quality was the OSM community that continuously contributes, maintains, and verifies data, leading to high levels of detail, coverage, and frequent updates. This theme was mentioned 9 times. Other top reasons that emerged were the open-source nature and free availability of OSM data that encourages continuous improvement, verification, collaboration, and widespread use by a diverse range of users, and transparency it fosters (8 times), and the robust systems for quality control and assurance (5 times). Among reasons questioning OSM’s high quality, the community approach emerged with a different sentiment: the heavy reliance on volunteers leading to inconsistencies. Other reasons mainly highlighted potential accuracy and quality issues, also supported by the lack of professional-grade surveying tools available to contributors. The models also rated OSM on 5 dimensions of geospatial data quality using a scale from 1 (Very Low) to 5 (Very High). The quantitative ratings indicate that OSM is perceived by chatbots as strong in temporal quality (avg=3.93, SD=0.8), while completeness (avg=3.33, SD=0.62) emerged as the most variable dimension, reflecting regional disparities in data coverage. Other data dimensions such as positional accuracy (avg=3.73, SD=0.59), logical consistency (avg=3.6, SD=0.63) and thematic accuracy (avg=3.53, SD=0.52) received comparable ratings, that suggests that none of the probed data quality dimensions are considered outstandingly low or high by the chatbots.

Temporal currency of OSM: When asked whether OSM is up-to-date compared to other leading providers of geospatial data, chatbots present a mixed picture with 7 responding “Yes” and 8 responding “No”. This indicates that chatbots lean towards slight skepticism about OSM’s currency relative to proprietary and authoritative sources. Top themes supporting high temporal currency were rapid updates facilitated by a large and active community and near real-time edits and corrections, often within minutes or hours. The chatbots answering yes generally recognized the crowdsourced model that can often

reflect on-the-ground changes more quickly than the scheduled update cycles of commercial providers. Other common themes were local knowledge that is more adept at mapping hyperlocal and informal features, as well as the open nature of OSM, encompassing open source software, open data and the editable, wiki-style model that allows anyone to contribute without commercial and proprietary restrictions constraining the framework. The main reasons questioning whether OSM is up-to-date were inconsistencies and the commercial advantage of other map providers. Inconsistencies were mentioned both related to the volunteer community and correspondingly the geographical inconsistency in areas with minimal volunteer presence. The commercial advantage was highlighted both in terms of resources available to commercial providers (e.g. dedicated teams, automated services) as well as the data sources they can utilize for generating geospatial data (satellite imagery, systematic data collection). The quantitative ratings reinforce this mixed picture. Chatbots were prompted to rate the typical update speed of OSM compared to major commercial providers for different feature types on a 5-point scale (1=much slower, 5=much faster). New Points of Interests (POIs) were rated the highest (avg=4.0, SD=1.0), indicating that OSM is generally faster at reflecting newly opened business, amenities or landmarks. New residential streets (avg=3.13, SD=1.19) and major highway changes (avg=3.0, SD=0.76) also scored reasonably well, which again suggests that OSM is often comparable or faster than commercial providers for important changes in the transportation network. By contrast, OSM tends to lag in more resource-intensive or systematically mapped categories: building footprints in urban areas (avg=2.73, SD=0.7), and especially land use changes in rural areas (avg=1.73, SD=0.7), where OSM is generally slower or much slower than commercial datasets.

Overall sentiment towards OSM: When asked to provide keywords that capture the main advantages and disadvantages of OSM, chatbots emphasized its global coverage, community-driven nature and the fact that it is free and customizable. These qualities collectively highlight OSM's value proposition as a crowdsourced, open and cost-free alternative to commercial providers. Other frequently mentioned strengths include OSM's reputation for being up-to-date, its open-source ecosystem as well as its potential for frequent updates and rich local details in areas with active contributors. The most common disadvantages reflect concerns about inconsistent quality, volunteer dependency and incomplete or variable coverage with gaps and risk of vandalism or errors. Several responses also pointed to a steep learning curve and potential technical barriers that may limit adoption among less experienced users, as well as the lack of official support or validation that commercial providers can guarantee. Despite the challenges, the overall sentiment towards OSM tends to be strongly positive. On a scale from -10 (overwhelmingly negative) to +10 (overwhelmingly positive), the average rating across 15 LLMs/chatbots was +7.07, which indicates that OSM is widely regarded as a valuable, reliable and innovative geospatial resource.

Overall, from our initial experimentation it appears that LLMs/chatbots do positively recognize the value of OSM. While it is not possible to discuss all of the results generated, it is recognised that the OSM community continuously contributes, has local knowledge, reflects on-the-ground changes, maintains, and verifies data, and this contributes to high levels of detail, coverage, etc. However, the OSM ecosystem that relies on volunteers can also lead to inconsistencies in these areas. Quantitatively, the LLMs/chatbots queried had no strong opinions either way on temporal quality, completeness, positional accuracy, etc.

Our results suggest that the sentiment towards OSM from the LLMs/chatbots queried is strongly positive and this indicates that OSM is widely regarded as a valuable, reliable and innovative geospatial resource. This positive sentiment can have a positive influence on users using LLMs/chatbots to explore OSM or evaluate OSM's suitability for a specific task. The primary limitation of this experiment is that LLMs lack genuine opinions as their outputs are statistical reflections of their training data. Methodologically, our use of structured prompts and deterministic parameters ensured reproducibility but constrained responses to a single, probable output, not exploring the models' full generative variability. Details about the included models, experimental setup as well as the data supporting these results are available at <https://osf.io/wc25k/>. There are some immediate considerations for future work. These include assessing the overall model size, measuring the consistency of outputs generated from the queried LLMs/chatbots, and potentially surveying human subjects about OSM in the same way as the LLMs/chatbots are queried for this work.

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